

Aerially Determined Dynamic Environment Mapping for Enhanced Road Vehicle Awareness

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Abstract

Autonomous vehicles require real-time data from several onboard sensors and cameras to navigate their environment. Aerial dynamic environment mapping information can provide additional detailed representations of a local road environment allowing for more robust operation of the algorithms utilised to control autonomous road vehicles. This paper proposes an OpenCV-based framework that utilises a YOLOv7 object detection model, trained upon a custom dataset achieving a mean Average Precision (mAP) @0.5 score of 95.6%, to derive dynamic environment mapping information from an aerial video stream. The framework detects and tracks cars, cyclists, and pedestrians, determining their instantaneous trajectories with an accuracy of 96%, 92% and 78% respectively. Real-time analysis of these trajectories allows for the accurate identification of potential collisions. The framework also accurately estimates each tracked object's geographic coordinates by comparing the aerial video stream with available 3rd party geo-tagged imagery.

Keywords: Aerial Environment Mapping Information, Location Mapping, Autonomous Vehicle, Machine Vision

1 Introduction

The reliable performance of autonomous road vehicles and driver assistance technologies depends heavily on real-time sensor and camera data, which can be limited by weather conditions, occlusions, sensor failures, positioning and orientation of the sensors/cameras. Aerially determined (e.g. using cameras deployed on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) such as drones and dirigibles) dynamic environment mapping (ADEM) information can provide an alternative and potentially more accurate and reliable representation of the local driving environment thus aiding autonomous vehicle software in making more robust decisions. Such a system, where cameras are deployed on a UAV to provide a “top down” view of a road scene, could be used to enhance or harden local environment mapping information provided by systems using infrastructure and vehicle mounted cameras/sensors. In addition, such an aerial based system could also provide a low cost and quickly deployable system for use in situations such as when temporary roadworks or traffic flow control restrictions are in place. ADEM could detect and track other road users and obstacles beyond the range of the vehicle's sensors and incorporate relevant data such as geographic coordinates. This paper proposes an algorithmic framework which utilises YOLOv7 and OpenCV to determine such dynamic environment mapping information from a video stream captured from an aerial (i.e. drone) platform. Figure 1 provides both a high-level overview of the proposed framework's architecture and a possible deployment scenario where all computationally demanding/energy intensive processing is completed on a cloud-based server with appropriate 5G network services (e.g. Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication) providing the required inter-connection between the system components. The proposed framework required the training and validating of a YOLOv7 model using a custom video dataset. An OpenCV-based algorithm was developed to detect and track these objects and to instantaneously predict potential collisions through the analysis of the trajectory of each tracked object. The framework also utilises Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT)

key-point matching in combination with Bilinear Interpolation to map each tracked object to real-world geographic coordinates.

Figure 1 – Overview of Algorithm Framework and Potential System Deployment Model

2 Related Work

The use of ADEM technology to enhance the awareness of road vehicles, particularly in the context of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), is a rapidly emerging area of research. Several studies have recently been conducted on object detection models for autonomous vehicle applications. YOLOv7 has shown promise in achieving high accuracy while maintaining low inference times, making it a suitable choice for such applications. YOLOv7 is an extension to the You Only Look Once (YOLO) family of object detection models and it has achieved state-of-the-art performance of several benchmark datasets. The YOLOv7 model improved upon previous versions of YOLO by incorporating a ResNet backbone, feature pyramid network, and enhanced anchor generation. It surpasses all known object detectors in both speed and accuracy in the range from 5 FPS to 160 FPS and has the highest accuracy 56.8% AP among reported real-time object detectors operating at 30 FPS or higher. [Wang et al., 2022]. The use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) in tandem with YOLO-based architectures for object detection in aerial imaging has been comprehensively documented in [Koay et al., 2021] [Luo et al., 2022]. UAVs offer the potential to collect a vast, encompassing quantum of detailed spatial information in real time at a relatively low cost [Fornace et al., 2014]. The deployment of UAVs for the derivation of ADEM in an automotive context is a relatively novel field. A localization technique using aerial imagery maps and LIDAR-based reflectivity for autonomous vehicles in urban environments [Vora et al., 2020] introduces the potential for environment mapping in an automotive setting. The framework proposed in this paper differs from that previous work in focussing on an object detection-based dynamic map, including mapping to geographic coordinates. A SIFT key-point matcher [Lowe, 2004] was utilised to perform this comparison, in a broadly similar manner to other work such as the use of SIFT for GPS location mapping at a street view level, in tandem with satellite imagery in [Yicong et al., 2017].

3 Algorithm Architecture and Implementation

This section details the steps taken to implement the core application features, including the acquisition and

training of a highly accurate YOLOv7 objects detection model. The design and development of an OpenCV-based application to facilitate object tracking, via the Simple Online and Realtime Tracking (SORT) algorithm, and instantaneous collision detection is outlined. The use of SIFT and bilinear interpolation to implement location mapping for tracked objects is also documented.

3.1 YOLOv7 Model Acquisition and Evaluation

Deep learning approaches use neural networks for feature detection of objects and their subsequent classification into one of a pre-determined set of classes or labels. YOLOv7 offers high accuracy and low latency compared to other object detection models, which makes it suitable for autonomous vehicle applications where lower inference times are particularly critical. For the application-at-hand, it was necessary to train a YOLOv7 model on a custom annotated dataset, as opposed to an open-source dataset such as the Microsoft Common Objects in Context (MS COCO) dataset. This was due to the need for accurate object detection from a “birds-eye” perspective, as opposed to the ground level view offered by MS COCO. A custom dataset was acquired through the annotation of 600 randomized images from our captured aerial video footage using the Computer Vision Annotation Tool (CVAT). A YOLOv7 model was then trained via Google Colaboratory for 200 epochs. The following metrics were obtained from the training process.

Figure 2 – (a): YOLOv7 Model Precision Curve – (b): Recall Curve – (c): Precision-Recall Curve

The precision curve shown in Figure 2(a) illustrates the proportion of true positive predictions out of all the positive predictions made by the model. The model is accurate with a precision of 90.7%. The recall curve in Figure 2(b) measures the proportion of true positive predictions out of all the actual positive instances in the data with the model achieving a 98% score for recall. The Precision-Recall curve graphs precision as a function of recall. The model recorded a mean mAP@0.5 score of 95.6%, as per Figure 2(c). For reference, MS COCO has a typical mAP@0.5 of approximately 60%. The confusion matrix shown in Table 1 summarizes the performance of the classification model by reporting the proportion of true and false positives across each class. This study focused on developing a framework to generate ADEM information relating to Car, Cyclist and Pedestrian classes of objects. The values on the diagonal of the matrix in Table 1 detail the correct classification rates for the three classes, highlighting that objects belonging to the “Car” class were detected with 100% accuracy, “Cyclists” were detected with 98% accuracy, whilst “Pedestrians” were detected with 89% accuracy. This performance metrics compare very favourably with reported recognition rates of other machine vision application in autonomous driving studies using COCO [Carranza-García et al., 2021].

3.2 Object Tracking using the SORT Algorithm

It is necessary to maintain a record of object speeds and angles of movement on a frame-by-frame basis to determine the instantaneous trajectory of identified Cars, Cyclists, and Pedestrians objects. The SORT

algorithm is an object tracking algorithm that uses a combination of a Kalman filter and a Hungarian algorithm to track multiple objects in video streams. Figure 3 provides a high-level overview of the SORT algorithm's operation.

	Car	Pedestrian	Cyclist	Background FP
Car	1	0	0	0.07
Pedestrian	0	0.89	0.02	0.81
Cyclist	0	0	0.98	0.12
Background FP	0	0.11	0	0

Table 1: YOLOv7 Model Confusion Matrix

when tracking multiple objects in a single frame. It boasts an average Intersection over Union (IoU) score of 0.6 and 0.8 and achieves a high Multiple Object Tracking Accuracy (MOTA) score, ranging from 60% to 80%.

3.3 Instantaneous Collision Detection

In the context of an ADEM, a vehicle's control software may wish to utilise the provided local environment mapping data to identify as soon as possible any "obvious" collisions which might be likely to occur. Once a given object is tracked, its instantaneous trajectory may be estimated using basic trigonometric principles.

The algorithm works by detecting objects in each frame of a video stream and assigning them unique IDs. It then uses a Kalman filter to predict the position of the object in the next frame. Subsequently, it associates the predicted with the actual position of the objects on the next frame using the Hungarian algorithm, the Kalman filter helps to smooth out the motion of the objects and handle occlusions, while the Hungarian algorithm helps to maintain the correct ID assignments. The SORT algorithm was chosen due to its reported high accuracy, particularly

Figure 3 - High-level Operation of the SORT Algorithm

Figure 4 – (a): Intersection Between a Trajectory and a Boundary Box – (b): Intersection Between Two Trajectories (R) Flagged as Collisions

Each object's speed and angle of movement was stored in data structures keyed on a tracking ID. The speed and angle of movement of an object was calculated based on how far an object travelled between frames and in what direction that movement occurred. Once each tracked object had a calculated instantaneous trajectory, any collisions could be immediately identified as an intersection between its instantaneous trajectory and another tracked object's boundary box or an intersection between two or more mapped

instantaneous trajectories, as shown in Figure 4(a) and Figure 4(b) respectively. An OpenCV algorithm was developed, which factored in several edge cases, including multiple collisions that occur on the same boundary box. Clearly, the accuracy of a predicted collision is directly dependent on the accuracy of both object's trajectories and their boundary boxes. An analysis of the accuracies of these components is detailed in section 4 of this paper.

3.4 Location Mapping

A key functionality of the proposed framework is the ability to tag identified objects with accurate “real-world” (i.e. GPS) coordinates. Whilst the aerial video stream may be geotagged (e.g. based on a GPS receiver on the aerial platform), this information may not be sufficient to provide an accurate regular grid structure needed for the bilinear interpolation process which estimated the GPS coordinates of objects in the video frames. In particular, inaccuracies in the estimated altitude of the drone may introduce significant errors or require complex aerial platform control functionality to address. In this framework, a SIFT Brute Force (BF) matcher was used to facilitate feature extraction and detection, as well as key-point matching. The performance of the matcher was enhanced via the use of a suitable Lowe ratio. A location can be accurately geo-tagged by comparing intermittent frames of the video stream to accurately geo-tagged images from a 3rd party online source (e.g. Google Earth). In the proposed framework, two images (one from the aerial platform's video stream and the other from the online source) are determined to be of the same location if there are 50 or more identified key-points between the two images. This threshold was chosen using an iterative approach on a limited target dataset representing Google Earth images of the general geographic location where the drone video stream was captured. Figure 5 illustrates this key point matching process.

Figure 5 - SIFT Key-point Matching Between Two Images of the Same Location at different times and from different camera positions

Figure 6(a) illustrates how the GPS coordinate information from the geotagged matched image can be mapped to corners of the frames of the aerial video footage. The GPS coordinates of individual tracked objects within the video stream were then determined using a bilinear interpolation technique with Figure 6(b) illustrating the final output of the implemented framework where all objects are identified, their trajectory estimated and their location accurately geo-tagged.

4 Evaluation and Performance

4.3 Accuracy of a Tracked Object's Trajectory

The overall accuracy of a tracked object's trajectory may be considered as the probability that the magnitude and angle of the tracked object's trajectory are both correct. This probability may be calculated using (1).

$$P(T) = P(S) \times P(A) \quad (1)$$

where:

- P(T): The probability that the object's overall trajectory is correct
- P(S): The probability that the object's speed is correct
- P(A): The probability that the object's trajectory angle is correct

The length of a given trajectory is determined by the speed at which the object is moving. The probability that the object’s speed is correct may be derived from the confusion matrix shown in Table 1. By assuming the probability of a given object being detected in a frame is an independent event, the likelihood that the object’s speed is correct is the square of the probability of the object being detected. The probability that the trajectory’s angle is correct was estimated by comparing the calculated angle of movement to the ground truth angle of movement (see Figure 7(a) for example) with the disparity between the estimated and “ground truth” angles yield a margin of error. Repeating this process over several instances of object motion in the video stream (for different object classes) allowed a mean margin of error to be estimated.

Figure 6 – (a): Corner Coordinates Mapped from Matched Geotagged Images – (b): Output ADEM

Figure 7 (b) illustrates the overall accuracy of each class for periods where the objects were moving in one of four different directions (as measured relative to the vertical axis of the video frame).

Figure 7 – (a): Comparison of the Expected Angle of Movement (Yellow) to the Calculated Angle of Movement (Purple) – (b): Accuracy of Trajectories Angle for Each Class

It shows that both the Car and Cyclist classes have extremely accurate trajectories. Pedestrians have slightly less accurate trajectories, primarily due to their lower detection probability. The results produced from this analysis suggests that the application has a valid claim to accuracy. Cars moving vertically or horizontally boast an average instantaneous trajectory accuracy of over 96%, with the accuracies of cyclists and pedestrians being approximately 92% and 78% respectively.

4.4 SIFT Algorithm Robustness

As outlined in section 3.4 of this paper, accurate GPS coordinate information relating to objects in the video stream may be estimated by first comparing frames from the video stream to 3rd party geo-tagged satellite/aerial imagery e.g. sourced from Google Earth. However, it is important to consider the impact that the satellite/aerial image quality may have on the algorithm performance.

The accuracy of the SIFT matcher is a function of image resolution and, hence, it was important that the SIFT matcher performs well even when operating with quite low-resolution images from a 3rd party source. An analysis was undertaken to ensure the accuracy of the key-point matching algorithm across a range of satellite image resolutions (from Google Earth). Starting with a 4K image, the number of key points detected by the SIFT algorithm was recorded. By reducing the resolution of the image, the number of matches could be compared

Figure 8: Robustness of the SIFT Algorithm over a Range of Image Qualities

over a range of image quality levels. From Figure 8, it is evident that higher resolution images provided better accuracy, producing more key-point matches. In fact, a near linear relationship between accuracy and resolution was found to exist. Even at 10% of the original image resolution, the SIFT algorithm still produces more than 100 key-point matches (bearing in mind the previously stated condition that, in this framework, two images are considered to be of the same location if they have 50 or more common key-points). Therefore, this particular evaluation provides a valuable result, as it illustrates the robustness of the SIFT algorithm (and therefore the location mapping functionality), even when utilising lower quality images for 3rd parties.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

This paper has proposed a framework to derive dynamic environment mapping information to support autonomous and assisted driving application streamed from an aerial platform. The framework utilises a highly accurate YOLOv7 object detection model, which is trained and validated using a custom dataset comprising annotated images of cars, cyclists, and pedestrians. The accuracy of the model was extensively quantified and analysed, with the model recording an mAP@0.95 score of 95.6%. An OpenCV-based application detects and tracks objects in the provided aerial footage, allowing for the calculation of a trajectory for each tracked object. Subsequently, any potential collisions based on the intersection of these trajectories could be detected. Analysis regarding the accuracy of these trajectories was also undertaken, with the calculated angle of movement determined to have less than a 5% margin of error with the ground truth. A system to map tracked objects to their real-world coordinates was also implemented using SIFT techniques coupled with Bilinear Interpolation. The coordinate mapping system was analysed for its performance when passed lower resolution satellite images, such as those which were retrieved from Google Earth. There is significant potential for future further development of this framework. Expanding the object detection model to support a wider range of objects would be required for deployment in diverse environments. There is also a need to analyse the performance of the model in non-ideal lighting and adverse weather conditions. Fully integrating the location mapping functionality with a wider aerial image source, such as Google Earth, and the deployment of a complete system possibly using an architecture similar to that suggested in Figure 1 would provide an excellent testbed for further investigations of the proposed framework. Further work could also investigate whether an edge-processing based architecture (with most

of the processing implemented either on the UAV or a road-side hub connected to the UAV using lower power radio links) may offer a better overall solution in terms of power consumption and UAV flight time. Lastly, a more in-depth review of data privacy considerations relating to the proposed approach should be completed though the processing of “top down” video streams arguably raise significantly less data privacy concerns compared to those associated with roadside and vehicle camera systems (due to the fact that it is more difficult to robustly identify and track specific individuals in a video stream from the UAV platform in our architecture).

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